

A formula for the Jacobi symbol

Pierre-Yves Gaillard

We present a self-contained proof of a known formula for the Jacobi symbol.

Here are some reminders.

Let p be a prime, a an integer and $n(a, p)$ the number of distinct solutions of the equation $x^2 = a$ in the field $\mathbb{F}_p := \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$. Then the **Legendre symbol** $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)$ is equal to $n(a, p) - 1$. Equivalently $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right)$ is characterized by the conditions: $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ and $\left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \equiv a^{(p-1)/2} \pmod{p}$. A proof of this equivalence is given in Proposition 9 p. 6. Note that it implies $\left(\frac{ab}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{p}\right)\left(\frac{b}{p}\right)$ for all a, b .

Let p_1, \dots, p_n with $n \geq 1$ be (not necessarily distinct) odd primes, let b be their product: $b = p_1 \cdots p_n$, and let a be an integer. Then the **Jacobi symbol** $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right)$ is the product of the Legendre symbols $\left(\frac{a}{p_i}\right)$, i.e. $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{a}{p_1}\right) \cdots \left(\frac{a}{p_n}\right)$.

If x is a real number, write $\lfloor x \rfloor$ for the largest integer $\leq x$. Here is the formula we want to prove:

Theorem 1. *If b is an odd integer ≥ 3 and a is an integer prime to b , then we have $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = (-1)^n$ with*

$$n = (a-1) \frac{b^2-1}{8} + \sum_{i=1}^{(b-1)/2} \left\lfloor \frac{ia}{b} \right\rfloor.$$

The proof will be given in Section 2 p. 4.

Let us derive the quadratic reciprocity for the Jacobi symbol (Theorem 2) from Theorem 1. The presentation below is taken from a text of Nolan Wallach:

<https://mathweb.ucsd.edu/~nwallach/Supplement4.pdf>

Theorem 2 (Quadratic reciprocity for the Jacobi symbol). *If a and b are relatively prime odd integers ≥ 3 , then we have*

$$\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) \left(\frac{b}{a}\right) = (-1)^{(a-1)(b-1)/4}.$$

Proof. Set

$$f(a, b) = \sum_{i=1}^{(b-1)/2} \left\lfloor \frac{ia}{b} \right\rfloor \tag{1}$$

and define the positive integers α and β by $a = 2\alpha + 1$ and $b = 2\beta + 1$. Theorem 1 implies $\left(\frac{b}{a}\right) = (-1)^{f(b,a)}$ and $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = (-1)^{f(a,b)}$. It suffices to show

$$f(b, a) + f(a, b) = \alpha\beta. \tag{2}$$

Consider the following finite subsets of \mathbb{Z}^2 :

$$S := \{(i, j) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \mid 1 \leq i \leq \alpha, 1 \leq j \leq \beta\},$$

$$U := \{(i, j) \in S \mid ja < ib\}, \quad V := \{(i, j) \in S \mid ib < ja\}.$$

Then $S = U \cup V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Indeed, the equality $ja = ib$ for $(i, j) \in S$ would imply that a divides i , which is impossible. Let $1 \leq i \leq \alpha$. Let us count the number of points of U with first coordinate i . For an integer j the following conditions are easily seen to be equivalent:

- (a) $(i, j) \in U$,
- (b) $1 \leq j \leq \beta$ and $j < \frac{ib}{a}$,
- (c) $1 \leq j \leq \beta$ and $j \leq \lfloor \frac{ib}{a} \rfloor$.

This implies that U has $f(b, a)$ points. Similarly we see that V has $f(a, b)$ points. Since S has $\alpha\beta$ points, Theorem 1 implies (2) and thus the quadratic reciprocity law. \square

1 Gauss' lemma for the Jacobi symbol

Write (x, y) for the nonnegative g.c.d. of the integers x and y , and, if $y \geq 1$, write $r_y(x)$ for the remainder of x divided by y . Note the formulas

$$\lambda(x, y) = (\lambda x, \lambda y), \quad \lambda r_y(x) = r_{\lambda y}(\lambda x) \tag{3}$$

if λ is a positive integer.

Let b be an odd integer ≥ 3 and let a be an integer prime to b . For any divisor¹ n of b define the sets C_n and D_n by decreeing, for $c, d \in \mathbb{Z}$, that

$$c \in C_n \iff 1 \leq c \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad 1 \leq r_n(-ac) \leq \frac{n-1}{2},$$

$$d \in D_n \iff 1 \leq d \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad (d, n) = 1.$$

Set $C := C_b$ and write $|X|$ for the cardinality of a set X .

Theorem 3 (Gauss' lemma for the Jacobi symbol). *If a and b are integers with $b \geq 3$ and a prime to b , then we have, in the above notation, $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = (-1)^{|C|}$.*

The proof of Theorem 3 will be given on page 4. We follow closely Section 3 in Pierre Cartier's article "Sur une généralisation des symboles de Legendre-Jacobi", Enseign. Math 16 (1970): 31-48. We tried to give more details.

Let a and b be as in Theorem 3 and set $E_n = C_n \cap D_n$ (where n is a divisor of b). We want to prove:

¹In this text "divisor" shall mean "positive divisor", and $x \mid y$ shall mean " x is a positive divisor of y ".

Lemma 4. We have $|C| = \sum_{n|b} |E_n|$.

Set

$$E = \bigcup_{n|b} \{n\} \times E_n = \{(n; e) \mid n \text{ divides } b, e \in E_n\},$$

where an element of $\{n\} \times E_n$ is denoted by $(n; e)$ (with a semicolon) — recall that (x, y) (with a comma) is the nonnegative gcd of x and y . Note that E is the *disjoint union* of the E_n .

Lemma 5. There are inverse bijections $C \xrightleftharpoons[\gamma]{\varepsilon} E$.

Lemma 5 will imply Lemma 4.

Proof of Lemma 5. It suffices that the formulas

$$\varepsilon(c) = \left(\frac{b}{(b, c)} ; \frac{c}{(b, c)} \right), \quad \gamma(n; e) = \frac{be}{n}$$

do the job. Note that the definition of the sets C_n and D_n given at the beginning of this section can be rewritten as

$$c \in C_n \iff 0 < c < \frac{n}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad 0 < r_n(-ac) < \frac{n}{2},$$

$$d \in D_n \iff 0 < d < \frac{n}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad (d, n) = 1.$$

The result follows easily from this fact combined with (3). □

Lemma 4 implies

$$(-1)^{|C|} = \prod_{n|b} (-1)^{|E_n|}. \tag{4}$$

It remains to compute $(-1)^{|E_n|}$. The result will be given in Lemma 6.

Let n be a divisor of b . There is a permutation u of D_n and a map $\varepsilon : D_n \rightarrow \{1, -1\}$ such that

$$ax \equiv \varepsilon(x) u(x) \pmod{n} \tag{5}$$

for all $x \in D_n$. Since u is a permutation of D_n we have

$$\prod_{x \in D_n} u(x) = \prod_{x \in D_n} x. \tag{6}$$

We easily check that

$$\varepsilon(x) = -1 \iff x \in C_n \cap D_n \tag{7}$$

and that

$$|D_n| = \frac{\phi(n)}{2} \tag{8}$$

where ϕ is Euler's totient function (see Section 3 p. 5). Multiplying the congruences (5) and taking (6), (7) and (8) into account we get

$$a^{\frac{\phi(n)}{2}} \equiv (-1)^{|E_n|} \pmod{n}. \tag{9}$$

Let N be the set of those divisors n of b such that n has a unique prime divisor. For $n \in N$ we denote by $p(n)$ the prime divisor of n .

Lemma 6. *If n is a divisor of b , then*

$$(-1)^{|E_n|} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{a}{p(n)}\right) & \text{if } n \in N \\ 1 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In view of (4) this implies

$$(-1)^{|C|} = \prod_{n \in N} \left(\frac{a}{p(n)}\right).$$

Proof. Write $n = p^k m$ with p prime, $k \geq 1$, m prime to p . We get mod p

$$(-1)^{|E_n|} \equiv a^{\frac{\phi(n)}{2}} \equiv a^{\frac{p-1}{2} p^{k-1} \phi(m)} \equiv (a^{\frac{p-1}{2}})^{p^{k-1} \phi(m)} \equiv \left(\frac{a}{p}\right)^{p^{k-1} \phi(m)} = \left(\frac{a}{p}\right)^{\phi(m)},$$

the first congruence following from (9). If $m = 1$ we get $\phi(m) = 1$ and thus $(-1)^{|E_n|} = \left(\frac{a}{p}\right)$. If $m \neq 1$, then $\phi(m)$ is even and we get $(-1)^{|E_n|} = 1$. \square

Proof of Theorem 3. Setting $b = p_1^{k_1} \cdots p_r^{k_r}$ where the p_i are distinct primes and the k_i are positive, we have $N = \{p_i^n \mid 1 \leq i \leq r, 1 \leq n \leq k_i\}$ and $p(p_i^n) = p_i$, and Lemma 6 entails

$$(-1)^{|C|} = \prod_{i=1}^r \prod_{n=1}^{k_i} \left(\frac{a}{p_i}\right) = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{a}{p_i}\right)^{k_i} = \left(\frac{a}{b}\right).$$

\square

2 Proof of the main theorem

Let us prove Theorem 1 p. 1. We follow the proof of Theorem 3.3 in the book *Introduction to the theory of numbers* by Niven, Zuckerman and Montgomery.

Proof. Set $m = \frac{b-1}{2}$. Let r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n denote the residues that exceed $\frac{b}{2}$, and let s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k denote the remaining residues. The r_i and s_i are all distinct, and none is zero. Furthermore, $n + k = m$. Now $0 < b - r_i < \frac{b}{2}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and the numbers $b - r_i$ are distinct. Also no $b - r_i$ is an s_j for if $b - r_i = s_j$ then $r_i \equiv \rho a$, $s_j \equiv \sigma a \pmod{b}$ for some ρ, σ , $1 \leq \rho \leq m$, $1 \leq \sigma \leq m$, and $b - \rho a \equiv \sigma a \pmod{b}$. Since a is prime to b this implies $\rho + \sigma \equiv 0 \pmod{b}$, which is impossible. Thus $b - r_1, \dots, b - r_n, s_1, \dots, s_k$ are all distinct, are all at least 1 and less than $\frac{b}{2}$, and they are $n + k = m$ in number. That is, they are just the integers $1, 2, \dots, m$ in some order. By the Gauss' lemma for the Jacobi symbol (Theorem 3 p. 2) we have $\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = (-1)^n$.

Note that the quotient of the division of ia by b is $\lfloor \frac{ia}{b} \rfloor$. Denoting the corresponding remainder by t_i we get

$$ia = b \left\lfloor \frac{ia}{b} \right\rfloor + t_i.$$

Recall that $f(a, b)$ is defined by (1) p. 1. Since $\sum_{i=1}^m t_i = \sum_{i=1}^n r_i + \sum_{i=1}^k s_i$, this implies

$$a \frac{b^2 - 1}{8} = \sum_{i=1}^m ia = b f(a, b) + \sum_{i=1}^n r_i + \sum_{i=1}^k s_i$$

and

$$\frac{b^2 - 1}{8} = \sum_{i=1}^m i = \sum_{i=1}^n (b - r_i) + \sum_{i=1}^k s_i = nb - \sum_{i=1}^n r_i + \sum_{i=1}^k s_i$$

and hence by subtraction

$$(a - 1) \frac{b^2 - 1}{8} = b(f(a, b) - n) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^n r_i \equiv f(a, b) - n \pmod{2}.$$

□

3 Additional proofs

To make this short text more self-contained we add a couple of proofs.

For any positive integer n let C_n be the group $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, for any group G let $G(n)$ be the cardinality of the set of elements of order n in G , and set $\phi(n) = C_n(n)$. Usually ϕ is called **Euler's totient function**.

Proposition 7. *In the above setting we have for any group G of finite order n :*

- (a) $G(k) = 0$ if k does not divide n ,
- (b) $\sum_d G(d) = n$ where the sum runs either over the divisors of n or over all positive integers,
- (c) $C_n(d) = \phi(d)$ if d divides n ,
- (d) $\sum_d \phi(d) = n$ where the sum runs over the divisors of n .

Proof. Part (c) follows from the fact that C_n contains a unique group of order d whenever d divides n . The proof of the other statements is straightforward. \square

Theorem 8. *Let G be a finite subgroup of the multiplicative group K^* of a field K . Then G is cyclic.*

Proof. Let n be the order of G and let the above notation be in force. We claim $G(d) = \phi(d)$ for every divisor d of n . This will imply that $G(n) = \phi(n) \geq 1$, and thus that G is cyclic. Let d be a divisor of n . In view of Parts (b) and (d) of Proposition 7 it suffices to prove $G(d) \leq \phi(d)$. We can assume $G(d) \geq 1$. Let $g \in G$ be of order d , let $g^{\mathbb{Z}}$ be the subgroup of G generated by g , and let H be the subgroup of K^* (the multiplicative group of K) consisting of all the solutions of the equation $x^d = 1$. We claim

$$G(d) \leq K^*(d) = H(d) = g^{\mathbb{Z}}(d) = \phi(d).$$

To prove $H(d) = g^{\mathbb{Z}}(d)$ note that we have $g^{\mathbb{Z}} \subset H$, that $g^{\mathbb{Z}}$ has order d , and that H has order at most d (because the polynomial $X^d - 1$ cannot have more than d roots in K). This implies $g^{\mathbb{Z}} = H$. The other statements are clear. \square

Proposition 9. *Let p be an odd prime and a a nonzero element of the field \mathbb{F}_p . Then a is a square in \mathbb{F}_p if and only if $a^{(p-1)/2} = 1$.*

Proof. Let g be a generator of the multiplicative group \mathbb{F}_p^* of \mathbb{F}_p (see Theorem 8) and set $n = (p-1)/2$. Note that $g^n = -1$ because $(g^n)^2 = 1$ and $g^n \neq 1$. If $a = g^{2k}$ for some integer k , then $a^n = g^{(p-1)k} = 1$. If $a = g^{2k+1}$ for some integer k , then $a^n = g^{(p-1)k+n} = g^n = -1$. \square